

Condensation of Dehydroacetic Acid with Diazonium Salts

D. R. Gupta and R. S. Gupta

Dehydroacetic acid (DAA) (I) exists in solution as a completely enolised species¹ (II) as the hydrogen atom at C₃ lies in close proximity to three adjacent >C = O groups and provides products(III) with amino-acids, primary amines, and related compounds²⁻⁴.

Structure (II) suggests that like phenols, it might couple with diazonium chlorides in an alkaline medium at C₃. It was therefore considered worthwhile to explore this possibility. Several diazonium chlorides of different aromatic amines have been coupled with DAA and the diazonium compounds described in this communication.

Procedure.—Aromatic amine (0.02*M*; 0.01*M* in case of products 15 & 16) was diazotised in the usual manner and the solution of the diazonium chloride was added gradually with constant stirring to a well-cooled alkaline solution of DAA (0.02*M*). After adding the whole of the diazotised solution, the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hr. The product was filtered, washed successively with HCl (dil.) and water, and finally crystallised from ethanol. Characteristics of the diazonium compounds are recorded in Table I.

The products 1-16 are red, brown or black. These are soluble in ethanol, acetone, and benzene, showing deep red or brown colour. These are, however, insoluble in alkalis. This property is in agreement with diazo compounds having phenolic group in the *ortho* position⁵, suggesting thereby that such diazo compounds must exist in a chelate form. The compounds 1-14 can therefore be expressed by structure (IV), whereas 15 and 16, by (V) and (VI) respectively.

1. Borson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 74, 5172.

2. Iguchi *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1959, 7, 323; 1960, 8, 1; *Yak. Zasshi*, 1957, 77, 1258.

3. Gupta and Gupta, *this Journal*, 1955, 42, 421.

4. *Idem*, *ibid.*, under publication.

5. Migridichian, "*Org. Syn.*", Vol. II, Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1957, p. 1518.

TABLE I

No.	Amino dissolved.	Formula.	Colour.	%Yield.	M.P.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1.	Aniline	$C_7H_7O_2N_2$	Red	26	116°	10.12	10.19
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	$C_7H_7O_2N_2$	..	28	96°	9.61	9.79
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	$C_7H_7O_2N_2$	Dull red	48	135°	9.52	9.78
4.	<i>m</i> -Aniline	$C_7H_7O_2N_2$	Red	35	155°	9.98	9.27
5.	α -Naphthylamine	$C_{10}H_7O_2N_2$	Brown	26	170°d	8.54	8.66
6.	β -Naphthylamine	$C_{10}H_7O_2N_2$	..	31	103°	8.53	8.66
7.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	$C_{7}H_6O_2N_2Cl$	Dull red	20	85°	8.96	9.13
8.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	$C_{7}H_6O_2N_2Cl$	..	22	135°	8.96	9.13
9.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	$C_{7}H_6O_2N_2Cl$	Bright red	27	90°	8.95	9.13
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	$C_{7}H_6O_2N_2Br$	Light brown	24	118°	7.84	7.98
11.	<i>p</i> -Iodoaniline	$C_{7}H_6O_2N_2I$	Brown	22	138°	6.97	7.03
12.	2,3-Dichloroaniline	$C_{7}H_5O_2N_2Cl_2$	Red	27	107°	8.11	8.21
13.	2-Methyl-4-iodoaniline	$C_{10}H_9O_2N_2I$	Brown	31	245°d	8.87	8.90
14.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	$C_7H_7O_3N_2$	Dull red	18	169°d	8.91	9.01
15.	Benzidine	$C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_4$	Brown-black	62	97°	10.22	10.33
16.	<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	$C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_4$	Black	52	137°	11.90	12.01

N.B.—'d' denotes decomposition.

[R = Ph, *o*-Tol, *p*-Tol, *m*-Tol, α - $C_{10}H_7$, β - $C_{10}H_7$,
o- ClC_6H_4 , *m*- ClC_6H_4 , *p*- ClC_6H_4 , *p*- BrC_6H_4 , *p*- IC_6H_4 ,
 2,3- $Cl_2C_6H_3$, *p*- $HOOC.C_6H_4$, 2-Me-4-iodophenyl].

The yields of these diazonium compounds are generally poor, possibly due to the following reasons: (i) An overall deactivating effect of -COMe group on the ring; (ii) weak phenolic behaviour of dehydroacetic acid ($pK_a=5.3$); (iii) steric hindrance due to -Me at C₆ and -OH at C₄. The above factors appear to decrease the rate of coupling. Consequently some of the diazonium salts change into its inactive anti-form(VII) which does not react with dehydroacetic acid, resulting in a poor yield as some unchanged dehydroacetic acid has always been found present in the filtrate.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF ROORKEE,
ROORKEE.

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